

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-TECHNOLOGY-Training Platform, Work Package 3 - Consolidating ELIXIR Training standards and best practices for Open science and Open education]

M3.8 Setup of the organisational structure and standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

The objective of this milestone was to establish a clear organisational structure and a shared, actionable SOP enabling consistent (co-)creation, review, publication, and long-term maintenance of ELIXIR Learning Paths (LPs) in TeSS. LP development in TeSS requires coordinated input across pedagogical, technical, and community domains; it is inherently multi-stakeholder, bringing together community representatives, the TeSS team, and [ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus Group members](#). Without defined governance, roles, and workflows, LP development risks duplication of effort, inconsistent representation in TeSS, unclear decision-making, and limited capacity to keep LPs up to date as training resources and community needs evolve.

Building on previous work on LP methodology and representation in TeSS, and on practical experience gained through pilots, this milestone operationalised the Editorial Board model (a General Editorial Board and LP-Specific Editorial Boards) and the associated procedures. In July 2025, [deliverable D3.2 provided the SOP \(v1\)](#), defining roles, interactions with the TeSS team and Communities, and end-to-end workflows for LP delivery and maintenance. From December 2025, a dedicated [request form](#) has been made operational to formally submit proposals for new ELIXIR LPs. Both the SOP and the request form are integrated and publicly referenced in the [TeSS LPs page \(Editorial section\)](#) and the [new TeSS Platform documentation](#) (intended to replace the current/previous documentation reference).

As an initial outcome of this framework, the first ELIXIR Learning Path has been published in TeSS ([the RDM Community Learning Path](#)), and two additional ELIXIR LP requests are currently under review. The formal request mechanism strengthens transparency and uptake, while early official publication demonstrates feasibility.

Overall, the approach improves coordination, reduces fragmentation, and supports sustainable curation through clearly assigned ownership and review mechanisms. Future updates to the SOP and supporting resources will refine procedures based on implementation feedback and broader community engagement.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

EB	Editorial Board
LP	Learning Path
RDM	Research Data Management
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

TeSS	Training eSupport System
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The workflow and governance model supporting the creation, publication and maintenance of ELIXIR Learning Paths in TeSS is outlined below. To provide both an intuitive overview and a more detailed representation of the process, two complementary visualisations are included.

Figure 1. High-level workflow of ELIXIR Learning Path creation, publication and maintenance in TeSS, highlighting key interactions between stakeholders, Editorial Boards and the TeSS platform.

Figure 2. Detailed workflow and governance model for ELIXIR Learning Paths in TeSS, including roles, key actions, decision points, and the composition of the Editorial Boards.

Supporting Documents

- **ELIXIR Learning Paths SOP** for Editorial Boards (**D3.2**): [Link to the SOP](#)
Integrated and publicly referenced in TeSS:
 - *TeSS Learning Paths page (Editorial section):*
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/about/learning_paths#editorial
(note: this page/link may be deprecated in the near future)
 - *TeSS Platform documentation:*
<https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/content/learning-paths/>
- **ELIXIR Learning Path request form** (submission of proposals for new ELIXIR LPs in TeSS): [Link to the request form](#)
Integrated and publicly referenced in TeSS:
 - *TeSS Learning Paths page (Editorial section):*
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/about/learning_paths#editorial
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(screenshot from TeSS Learning Paths page - Editorial section)

Creating ELIXIR Learning Paths

If you would like to create an ELIXIR Learning Path, [please complete this form](#). ELIXIR Learning Paths follow a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) to ensure quality, consistency, and long-term sustainability. [Further details about the process are available here](#).

After you submit the form, a member of the ELIXIR Learning Paths Editorial Board will contact you to discuss your proposal and outline the next steps.

(screenshot from TeSS Platform documentation)

- First ELIXIR Learning Path on TeSS: [Link to the ELIXIR RDM LP](#)
The RDM Community LP was developed through a series of coordinated events: [Link to events](#)

Dissemination Plans

The milestone outcomes and supporting documents will be disseminated openly through:

- TeSS infrastructure: ELIXIR LPs created and maintained under the LP Editorial Board SOP will be published in TeSS with the ELIXIR Logo, providing visible, concrete implementations of the ELIXIR LP Editorial Board model within the ELIXIR training ecosystem. The LP SOP and the request form are Integrated and publicly referenced in the Editorial section of the TeSS LPs page and the new TeSS Platform documentation (intended to replace the current/previous documentation reference).
- Zenodo: the ELIXIR Learning Paths SOP (v1) for Editorial Boards (D3.2) has already been published on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17252832>
- Training SPLASH website: dedicated pages present the Learning Paths project and will be updated as procedures evolve.
- Presentations and workshops: the ELIXIR LP Editorial Board model and ELIXIR LPs will be promoted through ELIXIR training-related meetings and community-facing workshops to support uptake and collect feedback.

Additional dissemination activities (e.g., thematic events and further publications) will be considered in the next Training Platform Programme (2027-2028) to sustain awareness and adoption.